

RELATIONSHIP OF SOME "TYPOLOGICAL" FEATURES IN CHRONIC COLOSTASIS

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The relevance of the problem. Colostasis (CS) or chronic constipation (CC) is a heterogeneous pathology that combines a complex of general and gastrointestinal symptoms [3]. Currently, the prevalence of CS exceeds the number of patients with diabetes mellitus and chronic obstructive pulmonary diseases, reaching 32.8% in old age [2]. What is alarming is the fact that in the last 20 years have not seen any further significant improvements in results observed [1]. The presence of multiple etiological factors of colostasis often makes it difficult to choose the optimal tactics [4]. This study is dedicated to improving immediate results.

The aim of the study is improving the immediate and long-term results of surgical treatment for chronic colostasis by optimizing surgical tactics.

Material and research methods. An analysis of the results of examination and treatment of 396 patients suffering from chronic constipation (colostasis) who were undergoing inpatient treatment in the proctology department of the Department of Surgery and Civil Defense of the AndGosMI Clinic and the Ellikkala District Medical Association of the Republic of Korakalpogiston was conducted.

The sample of patients upon admission was conditionally divided into two groups:

-comparison group -172 (43.4%) patients with CS in the period from 2015 to 2018, whose treatment was limited to subsequent standard patient management.

-main group-224 (56.6%) patients with CS operated on in the period 2019 to 2023, who were treated with an improved treatment and diagnostic algorithm, as well as a modified method of "immersion" invagination coloanastomosis.

To achieve the goal and objectives of the study, general clinical, laboratory, biochemical, instrumental and statistical research methods were carried out according to the protocols approved by the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan and Coracalpohistone.

Results and their discussion. ANDThe study is based on a prospective and retrospective analysis with the inclusion of material from the proctology department of the Andrei State Medical Institute clinic of 396 patients with chronic constipation for the period 2015-2023.

At the age of 18-44 years, the frequency of this disease was also close to each other, both in the comparison group and in the main one. In the comparison group there were 10.5% of men (n=18), 33.7% of women (n=58), and in the main group 9.8% of men (n=22), 29.9% of women (n=67). At the age of 45-59 years in the comparison group it was determined as 9.3% (n=16) in men and 23.8% (n=41) in women, and in the main group 7.6% (n=17) in men and 25.4% (n=57) in women. However, at the age of 60-74 and 75-89 years the number of the disease was observed less.

Taking into account the ratio of the main group to the comparison group, $p < 0.05$ was observed 1.3% more often between women and 1.2% more often between men. The ratio of women to men was often 3:1.

As for the duration of the disease, it was found that it occurs more often in the first year, while with a longer history there was a tendency for it to be less frequent. When we took the ratio of the main group to the comparison group, both among women and men, there was a reliable difference of $p < 0.05$. At the same time, a longer course of the disease was noted in female patients.

Patients with colostasis recommended for surgical intervention underwent such operations as colectomy, subtotal colectomy, sigmoid colon resection and hemicolectomy. Of these, 179 patients were from the main group and 134 patients were from the comparison group. It follows that sigmoid colon resection was performed in 46.9% (n=84) of patients in the main group, and comparison was performed in 43.3% (n=58) of patients in the control group. One of the least performed operations is right hemicolectomy. It was performed in 8.9% (n=16) of patients in the main group and in 9.7% (n=13) of patients in the comparison group.

Conclusion. Thus, pThe use of optimized surgical tactics for chronic colostasis made it possible to reduce the frequency of postoperative complications associated with surgical intervention from 25.3 to 16.2%, purulent-septic complications from 18.6 to 9.5%, and general complications from 19.4 to 8.4%.

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